

ISSN: 0975-833X

RESEARCH ARTICLE

POPULATION AND DEVELOPMENT IN JAMMU AND KASHMIR WITH COMPARISON TO INDIA: EMERGING ISSUES AND CHALLENGES FOR WOMEN

¹Pramendra Singh Pundir and ²Alok Kumar Singh

¹Department of Statistics, University of Allahabad, Allahabad (UP), INDIA and DST-CIMS,
Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi (UP), India

²Department of Statistics, University of Allahabad, Allahabad (UP), India

ARTICLE INFO

Article History:

Received 24th December, 2015
Received in revised form
27th January, 2016
Accepted 29th February, 2016
Published online 31st March, 2016

Key words:

Population Development,
Annual rates, Women.

ABSTRACT

University of Allahabad, India In this paper, we have studied the major reasons affecting the population, social and economic development of Jammu and Kashmir. In particular we have studied various demographic rates and compared them with the respective rates of India. Also we have mentioned the major challenges for women in Jammu and Kashmir.

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Citation: Pramendra Singh Pundir and Alok Kumar Singh, 2016. "Population and development in Jammu and Kashmir with comparison to India: Emerging issues and challenges for women", *International Journal of Current Research*, 8, (03), 28389-28397.

INTRODUCTION

India has acknowledged the importance of population and development since past couple of decades. India's population has crossed one billion mark at the end of the last century and as per the 2011 population census, it stands 1.22 billion (Census of India 2011). According to United Nations medium variant population projections, India will become the most populous country of the world by 2045 (United Nations, 2012), surpassing China. It is expected that India's population is likely to be stabilized during the second half of the current century. With the decline in fertility and mortality over the past several decades, India has progressed on the path of demographic transition, although the pace of transition varies by states. Jammu and Kashmir have good fertility levels as TFR of Jammu and Kashmir is 1.9 which is considerable as compared to India whose TFR is 2.3 (SRS 2013). Studies carried out in different parts of the world have shown that there are linkages between population transition and social and economic development. It is now well known that social and economic progress in any region is linked with the demographic characteristics of population.

**Corresponding author: Alok Kumar Singh,*

Department of Statistics, University of Allahabad, Allahabad (UP), India.

As such there is a need to understand population characteristics of Jammu and Kashmir which is not behind other states and India but its social and economic development is far behind other states and India. Major reason for above concern is violent ambience due to lots of political reasons. The present paper is an attempt in this direction. Important demographic and socio-economic characteristics inarguably the most beautiful state in the country is the state of Jammu and Kashmir. It is surrounded by the Himalayas and many other mountains range and blessed with deep valleys and breathe taking sceneries. Tourism was the main money churning in times when war was not a major issue in the Kashmir valley. The population of Jammu and Kashmir according to the 2011 census stands at about 12 million, making it the 19th most populated state in India. The state is located in the northern part of the country and forms the northern boundary of the country. The state is spread over an area of about 220000 sq. km. making it the 10th largest state in the country in terms of area. The population density of Jammu and Kashmir is about 56 per sq. km which is fairly below the national average, this is mainly due to the presence of snow covered hills and mountain ranges in the major parts of the state. The state has also been troubled by acts of terrorism and militancy by its neighbouring countries, Pakistan and China. The state has a growth rate of about 23% which slightly exceeds the national growth rate of about 17%. The population of the state is facing many issues

which are preventing it from prospering as a flourishing state. The literacy rate in the state is about 68%, a figure that needs attention from the government. The constant warring atmosphere and fear of attacks across the borders have impacted the prospects of education in Jammu and Kashmir. The sex ratio in Jammu and Kashmir leaves a lot to be desired as it lags behind the national average by a huge gap. The sex ratio will improve only if the government in the state makes efforts to elevate the way of life of women in the Kashmir valley. The statistics in the Jammu and Kashmir Census 2011 reveal facts that can be instrumental in planning for a better development plan for the state.

The capital city which is also the largest city in the state of Jammu and Kashmir is Srinagar. The languages spoken in the Jammu and Kashmir state includes Urdu, Kashmiri and Dogri. In total Jammu and Kashmir (JK) state comprises 22 districts. Age specific fertility rates are given by Table 1 which shows that Jammu and Kashmir have low fertility rates in initial ages and high fertility rates in older ages. Age specific marital fertility rates are given by Table 2. It shows that Jammu and Kashmir have high marital fertility rates at all ages. CDR, GFR, TFR, GRR, and marital rates are presented by Table 3. It shows that except total marital fertility rate all other rates are low in Jammu and Kashmir.

Table 4 shows that how literacy would affect age specific fertility rates and Table 5 shows the percentages distribution of current live births by birth interval and birth order. Child and infant mortality rates (0-4 years) are presented by Table 6 which shows that Jammu and Kashmir have good performance. Birth rate, death rate and infant mortality rate of natural division areas are presented by Table 7. We have observed that infant mortality rate is high in Jhelum valley and outer hills have high birth rate. Annual birth rates, from 2008 to 2013, are presented by Table 8 which shows that Jammu and Kashmir has low birth rates but from Table 9, it is clear that annual death rates of Jammu and Kashmir from 2008 to 2013, is lower than that of India. Table 10 and 11 shows that Jammu and Kashmir has better infant mortality and total fertility rates than India but Table 12 shows that sex ratio of Jammu and Kashmir is very low than India at initial ages. It shows good recovery at later years. The sex ratio of children of age group 0-4 years during the duration 2007 to 2013 are presented by Table 13. It shows that Jammu and Kashmir have very low rates than India which indicates poor condition of women in Jammu and Kashmir. Table 14 shows that how literacy would affect GFR and TFR.

Table 1. Age

Age-gr	India	J&K
15-19	28.1	4.1
20-24	194.3	78.0
25-29	149.7	131.7
30-34	63.9	96.3
35-39	22.0	41.7
40-44	7.4	15.8
45-49	2.0	3.1

Table 2. Age specific marital fertility rates

Age-gr	India	J&K
15-19	270.4	446.4
20-24	334.0	364.5
25-29	177.2	246.9
30-34	68.9	119.4
35-39	23.6	44.7
40-44	8.1	16.7
45-49	2.3	3.3

Table 3. List of vital statistics

	India	J&K
Crude birth rate	21.4	17.5
General fertility rate	78.5	60.9
Total fertility rate	2.3	1.9
Gross reproduction rate	1.1	0.9
General marital fertility rate	112.5	110.2
Total marital fertility rate	4.4	6.2

Table 4. Fertility indicators by level of education of women-2013

Age group	Education level																	
	Illiterate		Total literate		Without any formal education		Below primary		Primary		Middle		Class X		Class XII		Graduate and above	
	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K
15-19	70.0	55.4	23.6	2.7	100.9	519.5	70.8	0.0	41.3	8.4	18.9	2.5	12.9	1.8	15.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
20-24	262.9	164.6	179.9	64.2	253.4	194.9	261.0	258.8	239.9	167.5	200.3	108.0	145.5	50.1	101.7	23.0	111.1	30.0
25-29	172.0	169.1	141.8	118.7	162.5	184.7	159.2	184.1	147.6	163.5	143.4	151.2	142.2	132.6	121.4	76.9	125.5	69.5
30-34	79.1	108.2	56.3	89.4	77.6	300.4	53.5	85.8	52.3	90.9	53.9	81.3	49.8	88.6	55.4	87.5	73.8	100.7
35-39	30.5	55.7	16.0	28.7	23.7	27.9	17.4	25.7	15.0	16.0	15.3	31.9	13.8	33.7	12.9	25.2	20.4	32.8
40-44	11.5	18.6	3.9	12.3	13.7	13.0	4.5	15.3	4.6	12.6	2.9	5.0	2.6	21.3	2.6	21.9	2.3	1.2
45-49	2.9	3.5	1.1	2.3	4.7	0.0	1.2	9.4	1.1	1.1	0.5	3.2	0.8	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.5	3.0

Table 5. Percentage distribution of current lives births by birth interval and birth order-2013

Birth interval in months	Birth Order									
	2		3		4		5+		Total	
	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K
10-12	1.0	0.9	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	1.8	1.3
12-18	7.0	7.0	2.4	2.1	1.1	1.1	1.0	0.7	11.6	10.9
18-24	9.9	7.0	3.8	2.4	1.4	1.0	1.3	1.1	16.5	11.4
24-30	9.9	9.0	4.4	3.8	1.9	1.4	1.4	1.0	17.6	15.2
30-36	6.9	6.3	3.0	3.1	1.1	1.2	0.9	1.3	11.9	11.8
36+	22.7	25.7	9.9	13.2	4.4	5.5	3.7	5.0	40.7	49.4
Total	57.5	55.8	24.0	24.8	10.1	10.3	8.4	9.1	100.0	100.0

Table 6. Child (Aged 0-4 years) and infant mortality indicators-2013

Indicators	India	J&K
Child mortality rate	11	9
Under-five mortality rate	49	40
Infant mortality rate	40	37
Neo-natal mortality rate	28	29
Early neo-natal mortality rate	22	24
Late neo-natal mortality rate	6	5
Post neo-natal mortality rate	13	8
Peri-natal mortality rate	26	29
Still birth rate	4	5

Table 7. Birth rate, death rate and infant mortality rate-2013

Name of the natural division	Estimated vital rates		
	Birth rate	Death rate	Infant mortality rate
Jhelam Valley	18.3	5.8	45
Outer Hills	20.3	4.4	36
Mountainous	17.5	6.1	23
Total	18.7	5.5	39

Table 8. Annual estimates of birth rate 2008-2013

Year	India	J&K
2008	22.8	18.8
2009	22.5	18.6
2010	22.1	18.3
2011	21.8	17.8
2012	21.6	17.6
2013	21.4	17.5

Table 9. Annual estimates of birth rate 2008-2013

Year	India	J&K
2008	7.4	5.8
2009	7.3	5.7
2010	7.2	5.7
2011	7.1	5.5
2012	7.0	5.4
2013	7.0	5.3

Table 10. Annual estimates of infant mortality rate 2008-2013

YEAR	India	J&K
2008	53	49
2009	50	45
2010	47	43
2011	44	41
2012	42	39
2013	40	37

Table 11. Annual estimates of Total fertility rate 2008-2013

YEAR	India	J&K
2008	2.6	2.2
2009	2.6	2.2
2010	2.5	2.0
2011	2.4	1.9
2012	2.4	1.9
2013	2.3	1.9

Table 12. Sex ratio at birth (female per 1000 male) -2007-09 to 2011-13

Year	India	J&K
2007-09	906	870
2008-10	905	873
2009-11	906	880
2010-12	908	895
2011-13	909	902

Table 13. Sex ratio of children (age group 0-4)-2007-09 to 2011-13

Year	India	J&K
2007-09	914	884
2008-10	914	887
2009-11	914	872
2010-12	912	877
2011-13	909	881

Table 14. Fertility indicators by level of education of women-2013

Age group	Education level																			
	Illiterate		Total literate		Without any formal education		Below primary		Primary		Literate		Middle		Class X		Class XII		Graduate and above	
	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K	India	J&K
General fertility rate	79.2	74.8	78.2	54.8	90.7	115.2	98.6	96.3	89.7	73.7	76.5	61.1	66.0	46.0	65.7	38.4	72.5	55.2		
Total fertility rate	3.1	2.9	2.1	1.6	3.2	6.2	2.8	2.9	2.5	2.3	2.2	1.9	1.8	1.6	1.6	1.2	1.7	1.2		

Graph 1.

Graph 2.

Graph 3.

Graph 4.

Graph 5.

Graph 6.

Graph 7.

Graph 8.

Graph 9.

Graph 10.

Graph 11.

Graph 12.

Graph 13.

Graph 14.

Data Source

The analysis is based on estimates of total population average number of births, average number of deaths, total fertility rates etc. Data has been taken from SRS report, NSSO and census of India.

Emerging Issues and Challenges

Despite launch of various schemes aimed at improving the status of women in various spheres of life, the demographic imbalance between men and women has deteriorated in Jammu and Kashmir due to reduced sex-ratio and low literacy among the females thereby posing major challenges before the Government in the coming years. According to the Economic Survey, women constitute around 47% in the total population of Jammu and Kashmir and the development of women, no doubt, has been a part of the development planning progress right from inception of Five Year Plans but the shift in approach from welfare to development towards women took place in a focused manner in the 6th and 7th Five Year Plan. The 8th Five Year Plan promised to ensure that benefits of development don't by-pass women and the 9th Five Year Plan changed the strategy for women from development to empowerment and emphasis on preparation of separate Women Component Plan by identifying specific schemes/projects having direct bearing on welfare and development of women. The 10th Five Year Plan further strengthened the implementation of Women Component Plan. Moreover, the Women and Child Development Department in the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment has also enjoined upon the states to monitor closely the flow of benefits of various schemes for the empowerment of women on regular basis. "Though these initiatives have helped in improving the status of women in various spheres to a great extent but the imbalance still exists which needs to be addressed over the years", the Economic Survey said, adding "in the 11th Plan numerous steps were taken but the targets could be only partially achieved and in the 12th Plan the Government's priority would be to consolidate the existing initiatives and interventions relating to women, build upon the achievements and also move beyond to respond to new challenges". According to the Economic Survey, female population of Jammu and Kashmir slashed down from 47.15% of the total population in 2001 to 46.88% in 2011. As per the details from Census 2011, Jammu and Kashmir has population of 12,548,926 of which male and female are 6,665,561 and 5,883,365 respectively indicating a reduced sex ratio of 883 as compared to 892 in 2001. "The population growth in this decade was 23.71% while in previous decade it was 29.04%. The population of Jammu and Kashmir forms 1.04 per cent of that of India in 2011 and in 2001 the figure was 0.99 per cent and this difference indicates a much higher growth rate in comparison to average India's

growth rate, the Economic Survey said, adding "demographic imbalance between men and women, however, continues to exist and has further deteriorated in Jammu and Kashmir".

Conclusion

Sex ratio is an important indicator of the social conditions particularly with respect to women's status in any society. Low sex ratio shows indulgence of artificial interventions, distorting the biological trend and natural balance in terms of number of females per thousand males, which is an important concern in the present status of Jammu and Kashmir's demographic transition. It relates to adverse sex ratio as the ratio as per Census of 2001 was 892 and the same as per 2011 Census is 883, which is a matter of great concern and needs to be addressed on priority. Describing education as very effective tool for women's empowerment not only from the point of view of literacy but because of inter-linkages with other social parameters like population growth, health care and education of children. Despite its linkage to so many positive outcomes and the progress made over the past 50 years, female literacy remains low in Jammu and Kashmir as compared to men. Jammu and Kashmir's literacy rate has been increased by 13% in the last decade—from 55% in 2001 Census to 68% in the 2011 Census, while female literacy has been increased from 42.22% in 2001 Census to 58.01% in 2011 gender differential still exists both in rural and urban areas and is comparatively higher in rural areas. This can be attributed to a number of factors like lack of access to schools, parents feeling insecure about sending girl children to schools, their engagement in agricultural and other domestic activities.

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